

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT AT ZHAW

Research results from a university wide survey on how scientific staff manages research data in their everyday worklife

ZHAW Services Research Data

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TABLE OF

CONTENTS

01 INTRODUCTION SURVEY

02 SURVEY RESULTS

2.1 EVERYDAY CHALLENGES OF ZHAW RESEARCHERS

2.2 CHALLENGING AREAS: TOP THREE

2.3 CHALLENGING AREAS: OTHER AREAS

2.4 CHALLENGES IN DEPTH EXAMPLE: DATA ARCHIVING

2.5 ORGANISATION

2.6 COMMUNICATION: INFORMATION FLOW

2.7 COMMUNICATION: INFORMATION NETWORK

03 OUTLOOK

01 INTRODUCTION

SURVEY

This report provides a quantitative and qualitative analysis of Research Data Management (RDM) practices among ZHAW researchers. It summarizes the findings of a survey conducted in 2023 with 235 ZHAW researchers, exploring both the challenges and opportunities of RDM across the university. The underlying dataset of the survey is openly available on Zenodo.

ZHAW Services Research Data conducted this analysis as part of a pilot project aimed at better understanding the current attitudes and practices in RDM, as well as the challenges faced by individual researchers and organizational units. As the central support unit for RDM, we are committed to developing tools, services and infrastructure that enable researchers to effectively manage their research data throughout its life cycle.

The goals of the 2023 ZHAW survey were to:

- identify the challenges individual researchers encounter in RDM.
- identify the challenges organizational units encounter in RDM.

The survey was conducted in German, with invitations sent to registrants of the ZHAW's project database. In total, 235 responses were received from active researchers across all major disciplines and career stages. (The School of Architecture was excluded from this report due to a non-representative response rate.)

This report aims to provide a clear overview of RDM practices and challenges as experienced by individual researchers, influenced by their organizational contexts. Additionally, it examines the flow of information between ZHAW Services Research Data, individual researchers, and organizational units.

ZHAW Services Research Data

ZHAW Services Research Data is a central support unit dedicated to various aspects of research data management (RDM). It consists of members from ICT, the university library, and the Research & Development unit of the president's office, along with a core group of researchers who represent the research communities of each School and dedicate 0.2 FTE to RDM-related activities per School. ZHAW Services Research Data provides the tools, support, and infrastructure needed for effective RDM.

+ 235

responses were received from active ZHAW researchers, across all major research disciplines and career stages

2.1 SURVEY RESULTS

EVERYDAY CHALLENGES OF ZHAW RESEARCHERS

As the focus on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and research continues, RDM can become a complex and demanding aspect of a researcher's daily work. While it is well understood that increasing and evolving demands on RDM pose a challenge for researchers, we wanted to pinpoint where exactly these challenges lie. When we asked the question "To what extent do you find the following aspects of RDM challenging?" the responses confirmed our expectations: most areas were perceived as challenging.

Our commitment to Open Research Data (ORD)

Making research data freely available for anyone to use, reuse, and redistribute. Open Research Data is typically stored in repositories with appropriate metadata and standards to facilitate sharing and collaboration.

Our commitment to FAIR data

The FAIR principles are a set of guidelines designed to enhance the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of digital assets. These principles are widely adopted in data management and ensure that data is managed in a way that maximizes its value to the research community and beyond.

2.2 CHALLENGING AREAS

TOP THREE

The top three challenging areas of RDM are (1) Data documentation (including metadata and version control of research data), (2) Data publication and (3) Data archiving.

Data documentation

77% of the respondents rated data documentation as medium to highly challenging.

Data documentation is an important aspect of the FAIR data movement as it ensures both transparency and reproducibility. This increases the need for discipline-specific metadata requirements and version control of research data.

Data publication

68% of the respondents rated data publication as medium to highly challenging.

A successful publication is the highlight of any research project where all the hard work amounts to a tangible paper. Well-executed RDM is the foundation of any successful data publication; therefore, problems in this area may have arisen at any point in the research data lifecycle.

Data archiving

64% of the respondents rated data archiving as medium to highly challenging.

Data archiving is an often overlooked final stage of the research data lifecycle. Effective archiving facilitates future data reuse and requires good data documentation, data anonymisation and data encryption.

The top three challenges researchers face in Research Data Management (RDM) encompass the entire research lifecycle. The primary challenge is the management of research data, which includes documentation, publication, and ultimately, archiving.

2.3 CHALLENGING AREAS

OTHER AREAS

+ 62 %

Data Encryption

89 respondents find data encryption to be moderately to highly challenging.

+ 59 %

Data Anonymisation

100 respondents find data anonymisation moderately to highly challenging.

In order to identify critical areas of RDM as experienced by ZHAW researchers, we explored various aspects, all of which were rated by the majority as moderately to highly challenging.

Data encryption and anonymisation are both elements that have undergone significant transformations as RDM tools and are essential for complying with data privacy laws set by the Canton of Zurich.

However, practical aspects of RDM are found to be challenging, such as the correct sharing of data with third parties during a project, which must comply with data privacy laws. Additionally, researchers face difficulties in converting data between formats when switching software or preparing for data publication. An honest observation from the majority was that they found it challenging to avoid data loss.

+ Other Areas

We also asked about other key areas of RDM and whether they are seen as moderately to highly challenging aspects of everyday work.

- 58% find **Data Sharing** with third parties challenging
- 58% find **Data Conversions** challenging
- 56% find avoiding **Data Loss** challenging

2.4 CHALLENGES IN DEPTH EXAMPLE

DATA ARCHIVING

The overwhelming majority of respondents (64%) reported data archiving as a medium to highly challenging task in RDM. Data archiving (which we distinguish from long-time archiving) is a moderately complex procedure. Therefore, data and its organisation must be documented and reviewed in terms of protection requirements. Data sets may also need to be encrypted. Data access rights, ownership, and the transfer of these rights in the event of personnel changes must be clearly established. Additionally, the archiving period should be assessed based on the requirements of funding agencies, legal frameworks, and institutional regulations. The process of data deletion and destruction must also be clearly defined, with necessary steps identified within the archiving timeline. The challenges associated with data archiving are further corroborated by interviews conducted with selected researchers from various schools (departments). We identified that regulations and infrastructure (storage locations) are highly diverse and decentralised, varying not only from school to school but also between different institutes, labs, and research groups.

58 % of the respondents at ZHAW do not know the regulations when it comes to archiving their research data (5% did not respond).

Funding agencies as well as universities have established their own sets of requirements and recommendations for data archiving. Researchers must adhere to these requirements to comply with data privacy laws in the Canton of Zurich.

We asked the 37 % of the respondents who indicated that they are familiar with data archiving regulations, if they could answer the following question: “What happens to the archived data when the archiving period is over?”

Only 10% of researchers were able to answer the question. This indicates that many aspects of data archiving remain unclear, and researchers may not be familiar with their implications.

ZHAW GUIDELINES

ZHAW has clear guidelines on data archiving.

ZHAW Services Research Data offers a general checklist on archiving of research data as well as customized support. Moreover, it is of note that ZHAW is currently in the process of implementing a centralized infrastructure solution, which will address many of the regulatory aspects concerning data archiving.

2.5

ORGANISATION

ORGANISATIONAL SIDE OF RDM

In the ever-changing field of RDM requirements and tools, the organisational side of RDM plays an important role in communicating best practices and current standards and supporting researchers.

79 % report no responsible RDM personnel in their organisational unit

Currently, this poses a challenge in keeping the research community up to date with the latest requirements in RDM. Therefore, a responsible person in an organisational unit can help keep the whole unit up to date by becoming a communication bridge between the researchers and the centralised unit of ZHAW Services Research data.

81 % report that they either do not have or do not know if they have any standards and practices regarding RDM in their organisational unit

Having clear, documented standards and best practices covering all aspects of RDM mitigates guesswork for researchers and helps maintain data quality and the overall standard of research work. When 81% report either not knowing or believing there are no standards and best practices, the organisational unit fails to provide the necessary framework that could and should support researchers in their work. Another issue may be the breakdown of communication between the centralised unit of ZHAW Services Research Data and the researchers. Without the former mentioned communication bridges of RDM personnel in the organisational units, the standards and practices as outlined by the ZHAW do not appear to reach the researchers.

2.6 COMMUNICATION

INFORMATION FLOW

The support structure at ZHAW concerning RDM is based on a centralised model. Survey results indicate an insufficient information flow from the centralised support unit to the researchers. As the content is not well known to end users, our primary goal is to enhance the visibility of our RDM resources. In general the communication from the centralised support unit to the departments does not seem to work properly. As a result, researchers are obliged to search for the necessary information on RDM independently. It is likely that many researchers are unaware that RDM content is stored in the self-service portal and therefore may not seek out this information autonomously. To address this, we have added a second communication channel: the website, which serves as a guidepost to direct researchers using search engines towards our content on the self-service portal.

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

SELF SERVICE PORTAL

The self service portal is an internally curated information platform that provides services and knowhow to the researchers and students of ZHAW. It is the ZHAW policy to use the self service portal as the information tool of choice to reach the researchers and students of ZHAW.

All RDM content is offered on the self service portal, such as guidelines, check lists, and FAQs. NEW: All RDM content was updated, translated into English, and keywords have been revised and adapted for search engine optimisation.

+ WEBSITE

A website has been designed to serve as the first point of contact and to enable search engines to more effectively direct users to our content, bridging the gap from the web to the ZHAW Self-Service Portal.

<https://www.zhaw.ch/en/library/research-teaching/research-data-management/>

2.7 COMMUNICATION

INFORMATION NETWORK

The communication at ZHAW is based on a centralised networkmodel where the ZHAW Services Research Data unit keeps up to date with the developing RDM requirements and provides matching support, infrastructure and tools to the 8 departments. The ZHAW Services Research Data unit is located in the third space which comes with benefits and challenges regarding the information flow. While ZHAW Services Research Data is a neutral support unit, at times communication is not always well received or heard. We found it helpful to connect our centralised information network with a bottom up approach of adding local nodes into the departments. The centralised network approach is economical and yields high control of the information flow and the local nodes improve the information flow between centralised unit and departments.

This is why a bottom up approach is also important where Data champions in the departments share RDM knowledge and feed needs back towards the central unit of ZSF. Local nodes are ears and mouthpiece into the departments. During the period of 2023/2024 we established the local nodes within the context of swiss university project. The network of local nodes is the structure we invested in and will carry on into the future to better meet the needs of RDM for researchers.

OUTLOOK

Experience has shown that a robust portfolio of services in the research data management profits from the involvement of personnel embedded in the research communities at the departments. Activities such as the development of guidelines, best practices, and hands-on support should follow a mix of distributed bottom-up and centrally overseen top-down approaches. Future strategic advancement of the RDM service portfolio, thus, will rest on close alignment with local nodes at the departments. These oversee and communicate the needs and activities at each department. The ZHAW Services Research Data continues to provide extensive and generic support along the DLC. At the same time, domain specific RDM support will be conducted by local nodes and identified personnel with the necessary knowhow. This emergent network ultimately might result in the formation of cross-organizational communities that serve as a natural sounding board. They articulate needs regarding infrastructure, tools, support, as well as feedback on the currently existing services and strategic alignment of the ZSF.

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